

Golden Set

#	Authors	Title	Year
G1	Colomo-Palacios et al.	Competence gaps in software personnel A multi-organizational study	2013
G2	Garousi et al.	Understanding the Knowledge Gaps of Software Engineers: An Empirical Analysis Based on SWEBOK	2019
G3	Radermacher et al.	Investigating the Skill Gap between Graduating Students and Industry Expectations	2014
G4	Garousi et al.	Closing the gap between software engineering education and industrial needs	2019

Articles selected for mapping study

#	Authors	Title	Year
P1	Ahmed et al.	Soft Skills and Software Development: A Reflection from Software Industry	2015
P2	Almi et al.	Software Engineering Education: The Gap Between Industry's Requirements and Graduates' Readiness	2011
P3	Aunimo and Huttunen	A Model For Building Skills And Knowledge Needed In The Job Market	2020
P4	Benamati et al.	Aligning Undergraduate IS Curricula With Industry Needs	2010
P5	Colomo-Palacios et al.	Competence gaps in software personnel: A multi-organizational study	2013
P6	Garg and Varma	Software Engineering Education in India: Issues and Challenges	2008
P7	Garousi et al	Aligning software engineering education with industrial needs: A meta-analysis	2019
P8	Garousi et al	Understanding the Knowledge Gaps of Software Engineers: An Empirical Analysis Based on SWEBOK	2019
P9	Juvane et al.	Assessing Mozambique's Software Industry to Foster Local Universities-Industry Collaboration	2020
P10	Mlitwa and Marambire	The Software Engineering Course & Its Skills Development Collaborative Initiative Between The Cape Peninsula University Of Technology, The Industry And The Local Government In Cape Town, South Africa	2015
P11	Naim et al	A collaborative Model to reduce Gap between IT Industry and academia (CMR-GIA)	2019
P12	O'Leary et al.	Developing a Software Engineering Curriculum for the Emerging Software Industry in China	2006
P13	Oguz, and Oguz	Perspectives on the Gap Between the Software Industry and the Software Engineering Education	2019
P14	Pyster et al.	A Draft Reference Curriculum For A Masters Degree In Software Engineering: A Joint Industry, Academic And Government Initiative	2008
P15	Radermacher et al.	Investigating the Skill Gap between Graduating Students and Industry Expectations	2014
P16	Santoso and Putra	Bridging the Gap between IT Graduate Profiles and Job Requirements: A Work in Progress	2017

P17	Siddoo et al. 2	Exploring The Competency Gap Of It Students In Thailand: The Employers' View Of An Effective Workforce	2017
P18	Sivananda et al.	Industry-Academia Collaboration via Internships	2009
P19	Stevens and Norman	Industry Expectations of Soft Skills in IT Graduates	2016
P20	Tuzun et al.	Are Computer Science and Engineering Graduates Ready for the Software Industry? Experiences from an Industrial Student Training Program	2018
P21	Pham et al.	Onboarding inexperienced developers: struggles and perceptions regarding automated testing	2017
P22	Begel and Simon	Struggles of New College Graduates in their First Software Development Job	2008
P23	Benamati	Current and Future Entry-Level IT Workforce Needs in Organizations	2007
P24	Patacsil and Tablatin	Exploring The Importance Of Soft And Hard Skills As Perceived By It Internship Students And Industry: A Gap Analysis	2017
P25	Juvane et al.	Opportunities for Industry-University Collaboration: A Case Study From Mozambique	2016
P26	Hall and Sandelands.	Addressing South Africa's engineering skills gaps	2009
P27	Beckman et al.	Collaborations: Closing the Industry–Academia Gap	1997
P28	McGill	Defining the Expectation Gap: A Comparison of Industry Needs and Existing Game Development Curriculum	2009
P29	Scott et al.	The skills gap as observed between IS graduates and the systems development industry—a South African Experience	2002
P30	Trauth et al.	The IS Expectation Gap: Industry Expectations Versus Academic Preparation.	1993
P31	Dawson and Newsham	Introducing Software Engineers to the Real World	1997